

Studies on the Citrate Complex of Aluminium (III)

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Aluminium (III) reacts with citric acid at lower pH, forming a neutral complex and liberating three protons simultaneously. At higher pH range (above pH 3.1), the complex C behaves like a dibasic acid and dissociates to complexes C_1^- and C_2^{2-} in two steps. The equilibrium constant of the reactions:

are 1.948×10^{-5} , 3.225×10^{-4} , and 1.616×10^{-7} respectively.

The citrate ligand occupies the three co-ordination position and the other three co-ordination positions of aluminium are occupied by three water molecules.

Collete, Bertin, and Batch (*Ann. chim.*, 1952, 481, 531) have reported that Al^{3+} forms a 1:1 complex with citric acid. In the present communication, formation of the citrate complex has been studied with Al^{3+} by the method of pH measurement.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aluminium perchlorate was prepared by dissolving very pure sample of an aluminium foil with a known amount (weight) of standardised 70% perchloric acid. The solution was made to 500 c.c. Aluminium content was estimated as Al_2O_3 . The excess of free perchloric acid present in the solution was calculated from the concentration of Al^{3+} . The free perchloric acid was neutralised by standard NaOH solution after addition of a known amount of citric acid in the following experiments.

(I). An aliquot (100 c.c.) of the solution containing 1.0002×10^{-3} g. mole of aluminium perchlorate, 1.5×10^{-3} g. mole of citric acid, and 2.5×10^{-2} g. mole of sodium perchlorate was titrated against *N*/5-NaOH at 33°. The results are represented graphically by curve B in Fig. 1.

In another experiment, the same volume of the solution containing 1.5×10^{-3} g. mole of citric acid and 2.5×10^{-2} g. mole of sodium perchlorate was titrated against *N*/5-NaOH at the same temperature. The results are represented graphically by curve A in Fig. 1.

Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain very nearly the constant ionic strength in both the solutions.

(II). Another aliquot (100 c.c.) of the solution containing 1.0002×10^{-3} g. mole of aluminium perchlorate, 5×10^{-3} g. mole of citric acid, and 2.5×10^{-2} g. mole of sodium perchlorate was titrated against *N*/5-NaOH at 33°. The results obtained are represented by curve B in Fig. 2.

In another experiment the same volume of solution containing 5.0×10^{-3} g. mole of citric acid and 2.5×10^{-2} g. mole of sodium perchlorate was titrated against *N*/5-NaOH at the same temperature. The results are represented graphically by curve A in Fig. 2.

(III). A portion of the above solution (100 c.c.) containing 1.00×10^{-3} g. mole of aluminium perchlorate, 2.0×10^{-2} g. mole of sodium citrate, and 3.2×10^{-2} g. mole of sodium perchlorate was titrated against 0.1*N*-NaOH at 33°. The results obtained are represented graphically by curve B in Fig. 3.

FIG. 1

In another experiment the same volume of another solution containing 2.0×10^{-2} g. mole of sodium citrate and 3.2×10^{-2} g. mole of sodium perchlorate was titrated against $0.1N$ - NaOH at the same temperature. The results are represented graphically by curve A in Fig. 3.

DISCUSSION

As observed in the investigations of other systems, the pH of the system B in each case is lower than the corresponding pH in the system A. This indicates the liberation of acid due to complex formation between Al^{3+} ion and citric acid. The horizontal distance increases gradually in the beginning and then decreases. But after pH 6.0, the horizontal distance again increases. In experiment (II), the complex containing more than one citrate ligand is not indicated though the ligand to metal ratio is nearly 5:1 as the horizontal distance, which may be taken roughly as the measure of the amount of acid liberated, is practically not different from that obtained in experiment (I).

Calculation of Equilibrium Constant

The reaction taking place in experiments (I) and (II) is assumed to be

(1)

where C is the aluminium citrate complex. The charge of the complex, if any, is not shown. The equilibrium constant is given by equation (1-1).

N/5 -NaOH added in c.c.
FIG. 2

0.1N.-NaOH added in c.c.
FIG. 3

$$\frac{[C] [H^+]^n}{[Al^{3+}] [H_3Cit]} = K \quad \dots \quad (1-1)$$

By proceeding in a manner similar to that adopted in the study of cadmium citrate complex (Pattnaik and Pani, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 673) it can be shown that

$$\frac{\Delta[NaOH] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta [Ct]}{[C]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

TABLE I

pH.	Δ [NaOH].	Δ [Cr].	[Al(ClO ₄) ₃]	a/b.	%.	[C].	[H ₃ Cit].	[AlB*].	KX105.
2.5	0.01890	0.00149	0.008906	0.2181	2.4841	0.007256	0.004818	0.001650	2.886
2.6	0.02040	0.00163	0.008812	0.2660	2.6150	0.007577	0.004214	0.001235	2.308
2.7	0.02042	0.00163	0.008736	0.3046	2.6956	0.007749	0.003747	0.000987	1.694
2.8	0.02044	0.00163	0.008662	0.3558	2.7808	-0.007943	0.003276	0.000719	1.343
2.9	0.02066	0.00156	0.008586	0.4184	2.8924	0.008228	0.002753	0.000858	1.665
3.0	0.02064	0.00156	0.008700	0.4822	2.9402	0.008494	0.002289	0.000206	1.802
3.1	0.02070	0.00156	0.008463	0.5499	3.0959				
3.2	0.02057	0.00155	0.008407	0.6197	3.1807				
3.3	0.02064	0.00155	0.008351	0.6911	3.2911				
3.4	0.02073	0.00155	0.008303	0.7632	3.4012				
3.5	0.02065	0.00155	0.008252	0.8351	3.4941				
3.6	0.02043	0.00154	0.008213	0.9078	3.5649				
3.7	0.02025	0.00151	0.008179	0.9797	3.6367				
3.8	0.01991	0.00150	0.008145	1.052	3.689				
3.9	0.01991	0.00147	0.008119	1.127	3.745				
4.0	0.01915	0.00143	0.008083	1.204	3.783				
4.1	0.01867	0.00139	0.008074	1.282	3.803				
4.2	0.01814	0.00136	0.008054	1.362	3.844				
4.3	0.01781	0.00132	0.008041	1.445	3.873				
4.4	0.01705	0.00128	0.008023	1.530	3.900				
4.5	0.01636	0.00122	0.008009	1.615	3.907				
4.6	0.01454	0.00109	0.007971	1.876	3.956				
5.0	0.01324	0.00099	0.007945	2.049	3.971				
5.2	0.01201	0.00089	0.007927	2.213	3.977				
5.5	.01074	0.00080	0.007883	2.450	4.061				
5.8	.00937	0.00070	0.007847	2.653	4.084				
6.0	.00805	0.00068	0.007827	2.754	4.149				
6.2	.00879	0.00067	0.007809	2.883	4.202				
6.5	.00868	0.00065	0.007785	2.916	4.273				
6.8	.00862	0.00065	0.007766	2.852	4.309				

When the formation of the complex is complete

Hence

$$\frac{\Delta [NaOH] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta [Cit]}{[Al(CitO_4)_3]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \quad \dots \quad (2-1)$$

The values of n are calculated from experiment (I) by equation (2-1), as determined in the case of cadmium citrate system, and are reported in Table I. n is found to be 2.48 even at pH 2.5. The value of n gradually increases with increasing pH and becomes 3 at pH 3.1. Hence below pH 3.1, a neutral complex C is formed by the interaction of citric acid and aluminium ion with the liberation of three protons. The formation of this neutral complex C is complete at pH 3.1. The concentration of the complex C below pH 3.1 is calculated by equation (2) assuming n to be 3.

The equilibrium constant K is calculated as before by equation (1-1). The values are recorded in Table I. The mean value is 1.948×10^{-5} . The values of K are constant throughout the pH range.

Towards the higher pH range, n is greater than 3. The complex C therefore dissociates like an acid to complex C_i^- and a proton above pH 3.1.

$$\frac{[C_i^-][H^+]}{[C]} = K_i \quad \dots \quad (4-1)$$

It can be shown as before that

$$\frac{(n-3) \times [H^+]}{(4-n)} = K_i \quad \dots \quad (4-2)$$

The values of K_i , calculated by the above equation, are recorded in Table II. The mean value of K_i is 3.225×10^{-4} .

TABLE II

pH .	$n-3$.	$4-n$.	$K_i \times 10^4$.
3.1	0.0959	0.9041	0.8426
3.2	0.1807	0.8193	1.3920
3.3	0.2911	0.7089	2.058
3.4	0.4012	0.5988	2.667
3.5	0.4941	0.5059	3.088
3.6	0.5648	0.4352	3.260
3.7	0.6367	0.3633	3.497
3.8	0.689	0.311	3.511
3.9	0.745	0.255	3.679
4.0	0.783	0.217	3.608
4.1	0.803	0.197	3.238
4.2	0.844	0.156	3.414
4.3	0.873	0.127	3.445
4.4	0.900	0.100	3.583
4.5	0.907	0.093	3.084
4.8	0.956	0.044	3.443
5.0	0.971	0.029	3.348
5.2	0.977	0.023	2.680

Above pH 5.5, n is greater than 4 and hence C_1^- dissociates like an acid to another complex C_2^{2-} and a proton.

The dissociation and the dissociation constant are given by equations (5) and (5-1) respectively.

$$K_2 = \frac{[C_2^{2-}][H^+]}{[C_1^-]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5-1)$$

It can be shown as before that

$$K_2 = \frac{(n-4)[H^+]}{(5-n)} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5-2)$$

K_2 is calculated at different pH values by equation (5-2) and the values are recorded in Table III. The mean value of K_2 is 1.616×10^{-7} .

TABLE III

pH .	$n-4$.	$5-n$.	$K_2 \times 10^7$.
5.5	0.061	0.939	2.090
5.8	0.084	0.916	1.453
6.0	0.149	0.851	1.751
6.2	0.202	0.798	1.597
6.5	0.273	0.727	1.188
6.8	0.809	0.691	0.7087

In experiment (III), the pH of the system (B) is lower than that of the system (A). The curve B is similar to the neutralisation curve of a strong acid. The pH attained by the solution containing aluminium perchlorate by the addition of 21 c.c. of 0.1 *N*-NaOH is reached by the other solution by the addition of 1 c.c. of 0.1 *N*-NaOH. So 20 c.c. of 0.1 *N*-NaOH i.e., 0.002 g. mole of NaOH is consumed by the complex formed from 0.001 g. mole of aluminium perchlorate. The liberation of two protons indicates the existence of the C_2^{2-} complex.

The structures of the aluminium citrate complexes are similar to those of the ferric citrate complexes discussed earlier by the authors (Proceedings of the Symposium on the Chemistry of the Co-ordination Compounds, 1959, Part III, pp. 102-126).